

Paper 8

CLOUD BASED SMART DUSTBIN SYSTEM FOR METRO STATION**Chandana Sagar* , Pooja Sanil****U.G Student, Dept. of CSE Srinivas School Of Engineering
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Abstract:

RFID based Smart Dustbin System is a prototype model of next generation dustbin which would be highly equipped with sensors. This model mainly focuses on the security aspects. Some of bomb blasts during 2008 serial blasts in Delhi were placed in dustbins. After the blasts dustbins were removed from all the metro stations in Delhi. This is because dustbins are an easy way to put the explosives. In this paper we present a viable solution for dustbins at metro stations. We have built this prototype model of this smart dustbin system using RFID tags, RFID reader, Ultrasonic sensors, Geared motors, Servo motors, Arduino UNO, Raspberry-pi and solar panel for power supply. The system uses cloud based monitoring system for garbage monitoring. With the use of cloud based system there is no need of routine checking of dustbins. To make the system ecofriendly and preserve carbon neutral footprint of metro we are using miniature solar panel for power supply.

Keywords: RFID, Smart Dust Bin, Ultrasonic sensor, PIR Motion sensor, Solar Panel.**1. Introduction**

With an average daily ridership of 2.7 million passengers, Delhi metro simply don't house the facility as basic as dustbins premises. Till 2008 Delhi metro stations were having dustbins, but after 13 September 2008 serial bomb^[1] blasts, dustbins were removed from all the metro station citing security threads. But removal of dustbin is not a good solution. One more problem with dustbins on public places is that they needed to be checked frequently so that they don't overflow. Routine checks for cleaning the waste are not efficient has dustbin may get filled early and vice versa. So with the use of Ultrasonic sensors we ensure that dustbin is emptied only when it is close to filling. Delhi metro already uses RFID based tickets and smart cards for ticketing purpose. So there is no need to create new RFID tags for the purpose of using bins. The users with their metro smart cards could easily access these bins. To get the access of these bins customer could have to have register through their Aadhar card at the Registration Desk for the verification of their identity. Once they are verified, the authorities would have a full data base of each customer who is using the bin. So, even if by chance something happens the officials could have all the data of each and every user for that particular interval which could include users address, fingerprints, photograph, retina scan etc. This could help the authorities to find the culprits very easily.

Fig 1: System Architecture

2. POWER SUPPLY

To provide the power supply to our automated system we are using two Solar Panels^[2] of 5v output each. The cumulative output of both these panels would be used to charge the rechargeable lithium ion battery of 9v. This battery would be used to provide minimal power supply to our Arduino Development Board, Raspberry pi Development Board, RFID EM-18 Module and the motors.

We are using solar power as it is a renewable source of energy. This power source would also make our system efficient even in the remote areas where there is no source of power supply nearby. And since our power source is renewable source of energy, so it would be cost efficient too. We would be only requiring one-time setup investment which is also not very expensive to operate the system lifelong.

3. ARDUINO DEVELOPMENT BOARD

Arduino^[3] is a very cheap development board, which was developed in Italy for the first time. It has an ATmega328 microcontroller. It also has a 32 KB Electrically Erasable Programmable Read Only Memory whose function is to store the set of instruction in the form of code written in Embedded C Language on the Arduino IDE, Integrated Development Environment^[4]. It has 6 analog pins to take analog data as input. It has 6 PWM pins to provide us with analog output. It has 14 digital pins which help us take output as well as input data digitally. Except from the input/output pins it also has a bunch of power pins which include 3 ground pins, one 5v output pin, one 3.3v output pin and a V_{in} pin. The development

board is capable of taking of input power supply in 3 different ways which are:

- Through USB Serial Port.
- Through Vin pin present on the development board.
- Through DC input jack.

The best part about this development board is that it can easily interface with almost all the sensors present in the market. This quality of this board makes it most susceptible for prototype development.

Fig 2: Arduino development board

4. EM-18 RFID READER MODULE

RFID stands for Radio Frequency Identification. EM-18^[5] is a RFID reader that is basically used to read RFID tags and extra data from that particular RFID tag. This module basically functions on the concept of electromagnetic induction. Both, the reader as well as tag consists of a coil. The basic difference between these two coils is that the reader has an active coil, i.e. it is provided with an initial power supply while the tag has a passive coil. When the tag coil comes inside the electromagnetic field of the reader coil it starts conducting. When it starts conducting current starts following through the passive coil. This passive coil at one end is connected to an IC which has a unique identification number in Hexa-decimal format. When the tag comes in the range of the reader it sends this number to the reader which further forwards this data to the micro controller. The main objective of the micro controller is to check whether the person using the bin is authentic or not from the database at the cloud server. If the user authentic it grants the permission to the microcontroller to open the bin.

5. ULTRASONIC SENSOR

Ultrasonic^[6] sensor is a device that is used to measure the distance between a particular object from the sensor. It has a transmitter which transmits sound wave and a receiver that receives the same signal. The concept of calculation of distance behind this sensor is very simple. It basically calculates the time taken by the signal to come back after reflection from the object, multiplies it with speed of sound and then divides it with 2 as travelling double distance i.e. going towards the object and coming back from that object. Here we are using this sensor to find the distance between the garbage and the lid of the bin. So, as the bin starts filling the distance between the garbage and the lid would start to decrease, and when it will cross a certain level the microcontroller would send the data regarding clearing the garbage from the bin to the cloud server which can be easily forecasted on the frontend with the help of an app or a webpage.

6. GEARED MOTOR AND SERVO MOTOR

Geared motors^[7] are simple motors that have number of gears attached to it control the speed and power of the motor. Here in this model we are using this motor to open and close the lid of the dustbin with the help of L293D^[8] motor driver IC. We require a motor driver IC in this case because our motor requires (9-12) V power supply which our development board Arduino UNO cannot afford as it works on 5V power supply. So, our microcontroller basically sends a control signal which further is responsible for turning motor ON or OFF with the help of L293D motor driver IC.

Servo Motors^[9] are simple motors which are connected to a sensor that provides it with a position feedback system. As a result of this feedback system this type of motor is able to control its angular and linear displacement as well as acceleration and velocity. We are using this motor to open and close the lock system of the dustbin's lid. When there would be an authorized User ID tag swiped in front of the dustbin, the microcontroller would instruct the servo motor to open the lid. If the User ID is not authorized, simply the controller will open the lid lock hence, the lid of the bin will not open.

7. PIR MOTION SENSOR

PIR Motion sensor^[10] is nothing but Passive Infrared Motion Sensor. As its name suggests that its basic function is to sense motion in the surrounding. Here we are using this sensor to check whether there is any kind of movement inside the bin after opening the lid or not. If we would be throwing anything inside the dustbin it would result in producing motion inside the bin. Due to this movement our PIR Sensor would simply generate a HIGH digital signal which would be sent to the microcontroller. As a result of this microcontroller would mark that particular user has thrown something inside the bin and send this data to the cloud server which would be a maintained record for the authorities to easily find the culprit if anything goes wrong. Apart from this our PIR also has two 10K potentiometer on it. Both of them have their specified tasks designated to it. The task of the first potentiometer is control the range of the sensor. This simply means that, this potentiometer would specify the area which the sensor would specify the area which the sensor would cover to sense the motion. So, with the help of this potentiometer, our sensor will not sense any motion outside the bin. The task of second potentiometer is to set delay which simply means, for how long the sensor will provide the same response at the output terminal. Both of these potentiometers are very

important for the proper functioning of the sensor so, we have to set their values very precisely to get the correct output at the output terminal of the sensor.

8. RASPBERRY-PI AND RASPBIAN

Raspberry-pi^[11] is low cost, credit card sized, small single board computer developed in United Kingdom. The development board has a 1.2GHz 64/32bit quad core ARM Cortex processor. It also has an inbuilt RAM of 1 GB. We in install an Operating System on this board with the help of 0 a micro-SD card or a pen drive. It has 4 USB ports, 1 HDMI Port, an Ethernet jack, a micro USB port for power supply, 40 GPIO (General Purpose Input Output) pins to connect sensors through it. It is very compatible and helps to build IOT Projects very easily. Here we are using Raspbian operating system on this board which is nothing but a LINUX operating system specially made for this board. With the help of Raspberry-pi we would be handling the cloud server for this particular project. The main objective of this board would be to connect our hardware interface with the cloud server and this board would be connect our hardware interface with the cloud server and this board would only be responsible for the back-end part of the project.

9. AWS IOT CLOUD

AWS (Amazon Web Services) IOT Cloud^[12] provides secure, bidirectional communication between IOT devices and cloud. This enables us to collect telemetry data from multiple devices, and we can store and analyze the data. We can take benefit of the huge processing power at our disposal to take care of large no of requests coming from IOT devices.

10. DJANGO AND PYTHON

Django^[13] is a web development and CMS platform built using python. Server-side programming for the system is done in Django.

11. ADHAR API AND AUTHENTICATION OF SMART CARD

Role of Aadhar API^[14] will be pivotal in the identification and registration of metro card holders authorized to use dustbins. Computers will be required to connect and authenticate their Aadhar card with the help of fingerprint reader. Those persons which connect and authorize their Aadhar number with metro card will be allowed to use dustbins by simply swiping their card on the card reader present on the dustbin. Authentication of smart card will be done via cloud. But there will be fail-safe mechanism so that when the internet connection is not working the cards can be checked against the local copy of list of smart cards. Processing power of the raspberry pi device is limited so the data is sent over the cloud for authentication. But as a fail- safe mechanism we are having local authentication also if the internet connection is not working.

12. REGISTRATION DESK

A registration panel is there for Aadhar card authentication. It is made using Django at backend and makes use of Aadhar API's eKYC (Known Your Customer) feature for registration of users. The RFID tag User ID will be regularly uploaded on cloud on a central database. Raspberry pi will be regularly updated with RFID tag User ID's. This is in place as a fail-safe mechanism so if the internet is not working the tag id can be authenticated locally.

Fig 3: Aadhar API and authentication of smart card

13. ANALYTICS PANEL

There will be analytics panel on every metro station so as to monitor the garbage levels in the bins, so that there is no need of routine checking. Marketing use of individual ultrasonic sensor data it will represent the garbage level in a dustbin.

14. CONCLUSION

In the upcoming years India is going to get densely populated and more number of smart cities would overhead in the upcoming years. Due to large population density in those cities metro trains would be a major requirement for the means of transportation. So, these systems will help us to keep our environment clean near the metro station as well as inside the city with keeping all security aspects in mind. These systems will also help us in waste management. The authorities would also help us in waste management. The authorities would also have a track of each and every user which would help them to monitor the cleanliness in the city.

15. FLOW CHART OF THE PROJECT

Fig 4: Project flowchart

16. REFERENCE

- [1] Samrat Sinha; IPCS Special Report 27 “Major Terrorist Attack in India”2006.
- [2] Neel Mathews; Narendar Rao; Gowrisankar; Biswajit Pattnaik; G. Siva Prasad “Grid Tied Roof Top Solar: Problems, learning and solutions “First International Conference on Sustainable Green Buildings and Communities (SGBC),2016.
- [3] M. Banzi, Getting Started with Arduino. “O’Reilly Media, Inc.”, 2009.

[4] P. D. Minns, C Programming for the PC the MAC and the Arduino Microcontroller System. Author House, 2013.

[5] Grewal Kaushal, “RFID Based Security and Access Control System Using Arduino With GSM Module” IJEEE, Vol. 2, Issue 2 April 2015 e- ISSN: 1694-2310 | p-ISSN: 1694-2426.

[6] A. Ohya; Y. Nagashima; 1994 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, “Exploring unknown environment and map construction using ultrasonic sensing of normal direction of walls”.

[7] Jeetender Singh Chauhan, Sunil Semwal, “International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications (IJERA) ISSN: 2248-9622, Vol. 3, Issue 1, January- February 2013.

[8] Vijayakumar Kawde, “Automated Wheelchair Embedded System” International Journal of Research in Advent Technology, Vol.2, No.3, March 2014 E-ISSN: 2321-9637.

[9] Yahia Mukableh, Georgia Southern University, “Efficient Control of DC Servomotor System Using Backpropagation Neural Networks” Spring 2011.

[10] Jaeseok Yun, Sang-Shin Lec; “Human Movement Detection and Identification Using Pyroelectric Infrared Sensors” Year 2014 8057-8081; doi:10.3390/s 140508057; ISSN 1424-8220.

[11] Vheah Wai Zhao; “Exploring IOT Application Using Raspberry Pi” International Journal of Computer Networks and Application Volume 2, Issue 1, January-February (2015).

[12] AWS IOT Docs: <https://aws.amazon.com/documentation/iot/>

[13] Django Documentation: <https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/2.0/>

[14] Aadhar API: <https://authportal.uidai.gov/developer>